

1 **An Artificial Intelligence Model for Teeth Segmentation and Numbering on**
2 **Orthopantomograms**

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38 **Abstract:**

39 **Objective:** To develop a Deep Learning (DL) Artificial Intelligence (AI) model for the instance
40 segmentation and numbering of teeth on Orthopantomograms (OPGs).

41 **Methods:** Forty OPGs were manually annotated to lay down the ground truth for training two
42 Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), U-net, and Faster RCNN. These algorithms were
43 concurrently trained and validated on a dataset of 1,280 teeth (40 OPGs) each. The U-net algorithm
44 was trained on OPGs specifically annotated with fluid margins to label all 32 teeth via instance
45 segmentation allowing each tooth to be denoted as a separate entity from the surrounding
46 structures. Simultaneously, teeth were also numbered as per the Fédération Dentaire Internationale
47 (FDI) numbering system, using bounding boxes to train Faster RCNN. Consequently, both trained
48 CNNs were combined to develop an AI model capable of segmenting and numbering all teeth on
49 an OPG.

50 **Results:** The performance of the U-net algorithm was determined using various performance
51 metrics including precision=88.8%, accuracy=88.2%, re-call=87.3%, F-1 score=88%, dice
52 index=92.3% and Intersection over Union (IoU)=86.3%. The performance metrics of the Faster
53 RCNN algorithm were determined using overlap accuracy=30.2 bounding boxes (out of a possible
54 of 32 boxes) and classifier accuracy of labels=93.8%.

55 **Conclusions:** The instance segmentation and teeth numbering results of our trained AI model were
56 close to the ground truth, holding a promising future for its incorporation into clinical dental
57 practice. The ability of an AI model to automatically identify teeth on OPGs will aid dentists with
58 diagnosis and treatment planning thus increasing efficiency.

59 **MeSH Keywords:** *Artificial Intelligence, Deep Learning, Dentistry, Neural Networks,*
60 *Convolutional Neural Network, Intraoral Radiography*

61 **Graphical Abstract:**

62

63

64 Introduction:

65 Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be described as a computing power that can harness information to
66 predict solutions, allowing for the emulation of human-level intelligence by machines. This is
67 executed via two subsets of AI, i.e., Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL). However,
68 ML has the major drawback of being time-consuming and expensive due to a pre-requisite of
69 ‘feature extraction’ (Silva et al., 2018). This step is essential for machines to learn the expected
70 tasks which is a tedious process that requires time and manual input by a subject expert (Silva et
71 al., 2018). In contrast, DL has the advantage of performing feature extraction independently and it
72 only requires a limited amount of initial manual input to learn the relevant features (Silva et al.,
73 2018). It consists of highly interconnected nodes, mimicking neurons of the human brain
74 (Schwendicke et al., 2020; Umer and Habib, 2022). The number of layers in DL algorithms
75 corresponds to the amount of intelligence it is capable of achieving. And the level of intelligence
76 is directly proportional to the amount of training data. This is largely why DL algorithms are
77 considered to be ‘smart’; being a more complex application of ML techniques (Silva et al, 2018).
78 Hence, for a DL algorithm to impart high-level intelligence it requires a large dataset for training.

79 Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are DL neural networks that are specially designed for
80 image classification tasks (Howard, 2019). These are specifically modeled after the human visual
81 cortex and require input for preliminary training on a set of images with the relevant features
82 labeled or ‘annotated’ manually (Koch et al., 2019). Once sufficient training is achieved by running
83 an adequate number of labeled images through the algorithm, CNNs can carry out classification
84 tasks autonomously (McBee et al., 2018). Image classification is carried out by three methods,
85 these include object detection, semantic segmentation, and instance segmentation (*Figure 1*) (Koch
86 et al., 2019; Corbella et al., 2021; Adnan and Umer, 2022; Umer et al., 2022). In object detection,

87 teeth are localized and identified using bounding boxes, whereas, in semantic segmentation, fluid
88 outlines segregate the teeth from the background identifying them as ‘tooth’ (Corbella et al., 2021;
89 Adnan and Umer, 2022) Instance segmentation is a further extension of semantic segmentation
90 that allows for the segregation of each tooth from the background and identifying it as a separate
91 tooth class, such as ‘molar’, etc (Corbella et al., 2021; Adnan and Umer, 2022).

92 In dentistry, the most commonly used dental imaging modality are Orthopantomograms (OPGs),
93 which allow for the visualization of all anatomic structures in the oral cavity, including maxillary
94 and mandibular arches, maxillary sinuses, temporomandibular joints, etc (Leite et al., 2021). These
95 are widely being used for their greater field of view and a relatively lower radiation dose (Leite et
96 al., 2021). An AI-based software that provides an elaborate report containing all diagnostic
97 findings on OPGs would greatly improve the efficiency of diagnosis and treatment planning (Leite
98 et al., 2021). It would also increase the overall cost-effectiveness since AI can potentially detect
99 findings that may otherwise be missed due to human error stemming from limited clinical
100 experience or fatigue (Rodrigues et al., 2021).

101 The first step in the automation of diagnostic processes on an OPG is the accurate recognition and
102 numbering of teeth. This paper describes the steps that were taken to achieve this objective by
103 using two CNN architectures. The inception of this model has laid down the groundwork of a
104 software for the total automation of diagnoses on OPG in the near future.

105 **Materials and Methods:**

106 This study was conducted at Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan from March 2021
107 to July 2021. OPGs were retrieved from the radiographic database of dental clinics after obtaining
108 exemption from the ethics review committee (2021-6525-18570) of the institution. These OPGs

109 were taken between January and May 2021 at the dental clinics. The sample size was determined
110 based on a study by Lee *et al*, and a dataset of 1,280 teeth (40 OPGs) were deemed adequate to
111 sufficiently train the algorithms (Chung et al., 2021).

112 OPGs were selected via the non-probability purposive sampling technique according to the set
113 inclusion and exclusion criteria as follows. Good quality OPGs with fully erupted permanent
114 dentition (including third molars) and having no signs of dental pathology were included. While
115 the OPGs with artifacts, extensive restorative and prosthetic work and the presence of orthodontic
116 appliances were excluded.

117 These OPGs were scanned by Orthophos XG 3-D (Dentsply Sirona GmbH, Bensheim,
118 Deutschland) operated at 60-90 kV and 3-16 mA; with the dimensions of 2440x1292 pixels,
119 captured in gray level. The OPGs were downloaded from SIDEXIS XG 2.63 software in Portable
120 Network Graphics (PNG) format from the image database. The patient's demographics (such as
121 age) were checked using SIDEXIS software. Data confidentiality was maintained by assigning a
122 serial number to each OPG, instead of using the patient's medical record number. The patient's
123 identifiers were not disclosed at any point in the study. All data were kept in a database, which
124 was password protected and only accessible to the authors of this study.

125 **Dataset Annotation:**

126 The dataset was annotated separately for two algorithms, U-net and Faster RCNN. The LabelMe
127 annotation tool was used to annotate each dataset (Labelme, 2021) For U-net, fluid outlines were
128 used to delineate each tooth (instance segmentation), whereas bounding boxes numbered
129 according to the FDI numbering system (object detection) were used to train Faster RCNN (*Figure*
130 *1*). The annotations were carried out by two investigators (NHAD & FUMR) of this study. The

131 annotations by the first investigator were checked by the second investigator and vice versa.
132 Consequently, all annotations were re-checked by the third investigator (WBK) before training.
133 All investigators were calibrated on the use of the software before beginning the annotation
134 process. Any mistakes in the annotations were corrected prior to the commencement of training.
135 These annotations laid down the ground truth for training the algorithms and against which the
136 accuracy of both our algorithms were evaluated using the testing dataset.

137 **AI architectures used:**

138 Two CNN architectures have been employed in this study for the instance segmentation of all teeth
139 whilst numbering them using bounding boxes. Both algorithms, U-net and Faster RCNN, were
140 downloaded online (UNet, 2019; Keras-FRCNN, 2020). The preliminary codes of these algorithms
141 were modified to suit the requirements of this study, before commencing training. The U-net
142 algorithm consisted of nine layers, with four down-sampling layers and four up-sampling layers
143 with a middle layer forming the base layer, similar to that of Ronneberger *et al*, 2015. A simple
144 representation of the Faster RCNN algorithm is shown in *Figure 2*. An in-depth explanation of the
145 workings of the algorithms is beyond the scope of this paper and can be found elsewhere
146 (Ronneberger et al., 2015; Ren et al, 2018).

147 **Training, Validation, and Testing:** (*Figure 3*)

148 This study was performed in accordance with the Artificial intelligence in dental research checklist
149 by Schwendicke *et al*, 2021. Before training, each radiograph was resized from the original
150 dimensions of 2440×1292 pixels to 512×512 pixels. This was done to improve efficiency of
151 training whilst reducing the computational power required for the execution of algorithm training.
152 The training dataset (all 32 teeth labeled) consisted of 1,152 images of teeth (36 OPGs) for both,

153 U-net and Faster RCNN. The classes of teeth (according to the FDI numbering system) were as
154 follows: 11-12-13-14-15-16-17-18-21-22-23-24-25-26-27-28-31-32-33-34-35-36-37-38-41-42-
155 43- 44-45-46-47-48.

156 To further increase the dataset, the following data augmentations was carried out:

- 157 • Rotation of within 10 degrees
- 158 • Zoomed by a factor of 0.1
- 159 • Translated horizontally and vertically by a factor of 0.1

160 Consequently, U-net and Faster RCNN were trained separately but in parallel, using the same set
161 of data, annotated differently for each algorithm as mentioned previously. The training was
162 performed using GoogleColab, with random initialization of parameters (Google colaboratory,
163 2022) Twenty epochs were used to train U-net, whereas forty epochs were used to train Faster
164 RCNN. Training was terminated at the respective epochs due to saturation of the algorithms.

165 The validation dataset consisted of 128 images of teeth (4 OPGs), making our dataset of 1,280
166 teeth (40 OPGs) in total. Furthermore, 320 images of teeth (10 OPGs) unseen by the algorithms,
167 were used to evaluate the performance of the algorithms separately. The visual results of both
168 algorithms were superimposed and are shown in *Figure 4*.

169 **Statistical Analysis:**

170 The metrics used to assess the performance of U-net are: Intersection over Union (IoU), Accuracy,
171 Dice index, Recall, Precision and Loss.

172 The metrics used to assess the performance of Faster RCNN are: Classifier accuracy for bounding
173 boxes and Mean number of bounding boxes

174 Results:

175 The algorithms were successful in achieving the desired tasks at a comparable accuracy. The
176 performance metrics and visual results are shown in *Figure 4*. Various performance metrics were
177 used to measure the performance of U-net. These included: precision=88.8%, accuracy=88.2%,
178 re-call=87.3%, F-1 score=88%, dice index=92.3% and IoU=86.3%. The performance metrics of
179 the Faster RCNN algorithm were determined using overlap accuracy=30.2 bounding boxes (out of
180 a possible of 32 boxes) and classifier accuracy of labels=93.8%. As evident by our reported
181 performance metrics, our model performs the tasks of teeth segmentation and numbering
182 exceptionally close to the ground truth laid down by annotation.

183 Discussion:

184 The automation of teeth detection and segmentation is considered the most challenging and crucial
185 step in the development of AI-based diagnostic systems (Leite et al., 2021). The localization of
186 pathology to the causative tooth is also integral for clinical applicability of an AI-based diagnostic
187 model (Leite et al., 2021). Several studies have accomplished the task of pathology segmentation
188 on two-dimensional periapical and bitewing radiographs as well as three-dimensional Cone Beam
189 Computed Tomography (CBCT), using various CNNs (Zheng et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021; Cantu
190 et al., 2020). However, these are unable to localize pathology to the causative tooth, detecting
191 merely the presence or absence of pathology in the entire radiographic image (Zheng et al., 2020;
192 Ezhov et al., 2021). Hence, it is important that teeth identification task be accomplished with as
193 high accuracy as possible before training the AI algorithm to detect pathologies (Leite et al., 2021).
194 The AI algorithms in this study perform instance segmentation and teeth numbering tasks
195 exceptionally close to ground truth.

196 In this study, object detection was employed for the precise numbering of teeth. The algorithm
197 utilized was Faster RCNN, which specializes in the object detection task. Its predecessors were
198 RCNN and Fast RCNN and this algorithm is a more advanced and computationally efficient
199 version of its antecedents (Tuzoff et al., 2019). For the segmentation task, U-net was utilized since
200 this algorithm has been specifically designed for medical image processing. This algorithm allows
201 for the precise delineation and segmentation of teeth from a background of anatomical structures
202 on OPG using fluid outlines. It also has the advantage of requiring a relatively smaller dataset for
203 training (Ronneberger et al., 2015). Additionally, in this study, U-net was specifically trained for
204 the instance segmentation of teeth on OPG which is more advanced than the conventional and
205 more widely used semantic segmentation task (Wagner et al., 2020). Hence, this model identifies
206 each tooth separately i.e., first molar, second premolar, canine, lateral incisor, etc. This is in
207 contrast to semantic segmentation which identifies all teeth as ‘tooth’ using fluid outlines on OPG.
208 This translates superiority to our model since it performs two tasks in parallel by explicitly
209 localizing as well as numbering teeth. In a recent study, Silva *et al* employed Mask RCNN for
210 semantic segmentation and tooth numbering, reporting accuracy of 96% (Silva et al., 2018). Due
211 to the complexity and the high computational power required for Mask RCNN, it was not feasible
212 for us to utilize this algorithm. Instead, U-net and Faster RCNN were used, and were able to
213 achieve our study objectives adequately. In saying that, the exact measure of the adequacy of this
214 model relative to others is difficult to determine. This is due to the heterogenous experimental
215 conditions and performance metrics reported by studies, hence only those that reported metrics
216 similar to ours can be used for a valid comparison.

217 For U-net a wide range of metrics were reported, including precision, accuracy, recall, IoU to name
218 a few, this was done to allow for a comparison with the evidence already present in literature and

219 since different metrics allowed for a better evaluation of the segmentation task. For example, IoU,
220 which the authors considered an important performance metric to report was only reported by a
221 few studies (Leite et al., 2021; Chung et al., 2021; Nishitani et al., 2021). This metric allows for
222 the visualization of results and determines accuracy of overlap of the algorithm's prediction of
223 tooth with the actual annotation of tooth laid down as ground truth. The U-net algorithm in this
224 study achieved IoU of 86.3% (*Figure 4*). Some studies that reported this metric included Liete *et*
225 *al* and Chung *et al* with IoU of 95% and 80% respectively, for instance segmentation of teeth via
226 ResNet algorithm and Lee *et al* reported 87% for instance segmentation via RCNN algorithm
227 (Leite et al., 2021; Chung et al., 2021). It should be noted that these studies used different
228 algorithms to perform instance segmentation task and it is unclear if a direct comparison is
229 justified. Nishitani *et al*, however, employed U-net for semantic segmentation with IoU of 80.9%.
230 This can be compared to U-net's performance in this study however, it should be noted that a more
231 advanced task of instance segmentation was performed.

232 A few other studies have reported performance metrics similar to ours, with varied number of
233 images in their training datasets and are described as follows, for better comparison the unit of
234 analysis in the following narrative is OPG (Koch et al., 2019; Nishitani et al., 2021; Wirtz et al.,
235 2018). U-net algorithm in this study (40 OPGs) had a dice index of 92.3%, compared to 74% for
236 Wirtz *et al* (14 OPGs), 90% for Koch *et al* (1500 OPGs) and 84.9% for Nishitani *et al* (162 OPGs)
237 (Koch et al., 2019; Wirtz et al, 2018). The precision and recall of U-net in this study were 88.8%
238 and 87.3% respectively, whereas Koch *et al* reported 79% and 87%, respectively (Koch et al.,
239 2019). It is evident that the performance of this U-net model is better than ones reported in
240 literature so far. It should be noted that an increase in the dataset from 14 images (Wirtz *et al*) to
241 40 images in this study, lead to improved performance metrics (Wirtz et al., 2018). However, a

242 further increase in dataset to 1500 images (Koch *et al.*, 2019) did not result in higher accuracy,
243 perhaps due to saturation of the algorithm. Hence, a small dataset, as was evidenced by literature
244 is sufficient to train a U-net algorithm with relatively high accuracy (Igloukov *et al.*, 2018).

245 For Faster RCNN, since it only performed the numbering task, reporting accuracy was deemed
246 most important as it indicates the precise accuracy of numbering. The Faster RCNN algorithm in
247 this study (40 OPGs) performed numbering task with an accuracy of 93.8% whereas Mahdi *et al*
248 (900 OPGs) reported an accuracy of 90% (Mahdi *et al.*, 2020). The optimal performance of this
249 Faster RCNN is evident however, due to the difference in metrics further comparison is not
250 possible at this point. It can be speculated that the higher accuracy of Faster RCNN in this study,
251 despite a considerably smaller dataset, could be due to the training dataset of essentially ‘perfect’
252 OPGs, with a full set of teeth and no pathology or restorative work. A consequent testing of this
253 algorithm on ‘imperfect’ OPGs is speculated to lead to a decreased accuracy. Other studies that
254 carried out tasks similar to ours but are not included in this narrative either due to the use of
255 different radiographic modalities, algorithms or performance metrics and hence a direct
256 comparison to was not possible.

257 The limited dataset of this study and the fact that these images were obtained from only one center,
258 can be considered as limitations however, these are drawbacks that can be curbed by adding more
259 images to the dataset obtained from multiple centers. Moreover, as stated earlier, OPGs with no
260 radiographic findings; those with a full set of healthy and fully erupted permanent teeth were
261 included in the training and testing datasets. This could mean that the performances of the
262 algorithms might not be optimum on OPGs acquired from a different center that has different
263 image dimensions and those with missing teeth for example (Askar *et al.*, 2021). More work to

264 include OPGs with radiographic findings, especially those obtained from other centers to make the
265 results of these algorithms more generalizable in the future (Askar et al., 2021).

266 The annotation of OPGs was carried out by an endodontist and consequently re-checked by another
267 endodontist. Other studies have used the expertise of oral maxillofacial radiologists, however,
268 since the task for this study was merely annotation of teeth, it was not difficult to achieve for
269 endodontists (Leite et al., 2021; Tuzoff et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2020; Muramatsu et al., 2021).
270 Hence, the ground truth was laid down by two experts that were calibrated on the usage of the
271 annotation software. In the future, a subject specialist may be hired for more complex annotation.

272 It should be noted that the performances of algorithms in literature were all reported against their
273 respective ground truths i.e., the manual annotation. Some of which were laid down by subject
274 specialists or radiologists, etc. Hence the reporting of performance is only as good as the annotation
275 that was used to train the model and there is no standard against which the annotation can be judged
276 (Umer and Habib, 2022). This makes for a lot of uncertainties that need to be addressed if AI and
277 DL techniques are to be employed in clinical practice for real-life application.

278 Another aspect that needs more clarity is the exact level of accuracy required for the model to
279 achieve to be deemed adequate for practical application. To the best of our knowledge, no such
280 report exists that would provide a cut-off point indicating the minimum required accuracy. Also
281 needed is a list of metrics that need to be reported relative to the algorithm being used for
282 standardization in reporting the performance of each type of algorithm. In addition, there is a need
283 to determine the performance metrics that better reflect the clinical applicability of the AI
284 algorithm.¹⁸ This will also allow for effective comparison of algorithms in the future in a real-life
285 setting.

286 Conclusion

287 The pertinent task of teeth detection has to be achieved before training the AI model to segment
288 pathology. This is needed for localization of the pathologies to their causative tooth/teeth. Within
289 the limitations of this study, we have managed to achieve our object of instance segmentation and
290 teeth numbering on OPG with high accuracy. Both our algorithms sufficiently perform the tasks
291 set out for them as evident by the performance metrics. This preliminary validation study has set
292 foundations for the actualization of a fully functionally AI-based diagnostic model that will be able
293 to detect pathology as well as localize the causative tooth/teeth in the near future.

294

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374

375 **FIGURES:**

376

377 **Figure 1:**

378 Convolutional Neural Network tasks:

379 (a) Object detection via bounding boxes

380 (b) Semantic segmentation via fluid outlines identifying all teeth as a single entity

381 (c) Instance segmentation via fluid outlines identifying each tooth as a different entity

382

383
 384 **Figure 2:**
 385 Simplistic representation of Faster RCNN algorithm training.
 386

387
 388 **Figure 3:**
 389 Workflow of training, validation and testing of the untrained U-net and Faster RCNN algorithms.

Algorithm	U-net	Faster RCNN
Performance metrics	Precision: 88.8% Accuracy: 88.2% Recall/ sensitivity: 87.3% F-1 score: 88.0% Dice index: 92.3% IoU: 86.3% Loss: 0.08%	Classifier accuracy for bounding boxes: 93.8% Mean number of bounding boxes: 30.2
Visual results		
Superimposed visual results		

392 **Figure 4:**
393 Performance metrics and superimposed results of trained U-net and Faster RCNN algorithms.
394
395